

Research into the problem of the influence of artificial intelligence on the consciousness of the individual and society

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Аннотация. В современной геополитической ситуации риски негативного влияния искусственного интеллекта на цивилизационные ценности российского общества существенно возросли. Они реализуются через формирование ценностных установок в сознании отдельных индивидов, их различных групп и общества в целом. Поэтому исследуемая проблема как никогда актуальна. Целью статьи является получение оценочных характеристик такого влияния и выявление возможностей его минимизации. Для ее достижения использован системный инструментарий, позволяющий принимать адекватные ситуативные управленческие решения. Проведено экспериментальное исследование проблемы смещения оценок под влиянием манипулятивности искусственного интеллекта с учетом факторов «индивидуализм-коллективизм» и «макиавеллизм». Получены сравнительные характеристики небольших выборок по контрольным группам индивидов и группам условных «личностей», сгенерированных искусственным интеллектом. По фактору «индивидуализм-коллективизм» смещение оценок под влиянием манипулятивности ИИ отсутствует с бесспорным для любых принятых уровней значимости сжатием вариативности. По фактору «макиавеллизм» (мера манипулятивности) смещение оценок, сгенерированных ИИ групп условных «личностей», значимо отличается от аналогичных показателей контрольных групп индивидов. Сделан вывод о необходимости проведения новых исследований манипулятивного воздействия ИИ на общественное сознание по фактору «макиавеллизм», равно как и по другим значимым факторам.

Abstract. In the current geopolitical situation, the risks of negative impact of artificial intelligence on the civilizational values of Russian society have increased significantly. They are realized through the formation of value attitudes in the minds of individuals, their various groups and society as a whole. Therefore, the problem under study is more relevant than ever. The purpose of the article is to obtain evaluative characteristics of such influence and identify opportunities for its minimization. To achieve this, a systemic toolkit was used that allows making adequate situational management decisions. An experimental study of the problem of bias in assessments under the influence of artificial intelligence manipulateness was conducted, taking into account the factors of "individualism-collectivism" and "Machiavellianism". Comparative characteristics of small samples were obtained for control groups of individuals and groups of conditional "personalities" generated by artificial intelligence. According to the factor "individualism-collectivism", there is no bias in assessments under the influence of AI manipulateness with an indisputable compression of variability for any accepted levels of significance. According to the "Machiavellianism" factor (a measure of manipulateness), the bias of the assessments generated by the AI of groups of conditional "personalities" differs significantly from similar indicators of control groups of individuals. A conclusion is made about the need to conduct new studies of the manipulative impact of AI on public consciousness according to the "Machiavellianism" factor, as well as other significant factors.

Ключевые слова: общество, цивилизационные ценности, индивид, сознание, искусственный интеллект, манипулятивность, факторы, смещение оценок.

Keywords: society, civilizational values, individual, consciousness, artificial intelligence, manipulateness, factors, bias of assessments.

Introduction

System modeling of the impact of generative algorithms of artificial intelligence (hereinafter referred to as AI) on socio-economic progress was performed by the authors in works [1] and [2]. It was found that the use of compressive diversity for assessing the actions of agents taking into account errors satisfying Fisher's evolutionary assumptions entails a slowdown in economic growth [1]. A model is presented for a fundamentally different situation taking into account obviously asymmetrical estimation

errors [2]. At the same time, the presence of an optimal narrowing of the diversity of estimates synchronized with the chaos of the environment was revealed. A conclusion was made about the need for a differentiated approach to the possible narrowing of diversity and the shift in estimates of groups of individuals under the influence of generative AI.

Currently, there are individual results of assessing the impact of AI on control groups of individuals, taking into account a number of factors. Of greatest interest to our study are the proposals on the

need to test AI algorithms for compliance with "socialist values" (the experience of China) [3]. In relation to our study, this means the need to test AI algorithms in order to identify random or targeted attempts to change the basic values of the Russian civilizational model and attempts to shift it to the Western "Anglo-Saxon" model. Experimental assessments of the impact of AI algorithms on the consciousness of various groups of individuals were obtained in [4]. However, the above and many other works do not provide systemic approaches to obtaining such assessments.

Based on the generalization of such studies and the interpretation of their results in the language of mathematics, the problem under study can be reduced to the use of economic and mathematical methods and sociological surveys to study the bias of estimates, narrowing their variability and deliberate and/or random manipulation of AI algorithms.

Since effective testing cannot be carried out with all existing sets of factors, it is advisable to select several fundamentally significant factors. But at the moment there are no systematized studies in this area. This study proposes to take into account the influence of two basic factors:

1) "individualism-collectivism" (hereinafter referred to as I-C), since it corresponds to the axiom "on the measure of chaos-order" as the main one for living systems;

2) the most important and universal factor of manipulability, implemented in the form of a test.

For an experimental study of the impact of existing AI algorithms on the consciousness of selected groups of individuals, well-known "human" tests and standard methods for assessing their results will be used. The approach proposed by the authors does not exclude the possibility of using other methods in further research that allow for full consideration of the entire set of factors and features of existing and new AI algorithms.

Literature Review

The results of scientific research by a number of Russian and foreign authors are systematized in two directions.

1. Research into the possible narrowing of diversity and bias in assessments of the impact of AI algorithms on human behavior.

The dynamics of changes in modern socio-economic processes show that there are trends that pose a danger to the development of humanity. It lies in the possibility of manipulating the consciousness of both an individual and society as a whole. It is carried out by influencing the cognitive abilities of a person using AI algorithms in order to control his behavior. Thus, the generation of content on the English-language Internet by a set of keywords allows its developers to adapt their prejudices and fictions to their perception in the public consciousness without any verification. The targeted use of language models facilitates the rapid spread of disinformation, which has a negative impact on the consciousness of an individual and society. As a result, individuals lose the ability to distinguish lies from truth and allow their consciousness to be easily manipulated.

Today, there is much research focused on the impact of AI algorithms on information manipulation, both random and/or systematic. AI is embedded in many everyday technologies, such as smartphones and social networks. On the one hand, they are extremely necessary for people, but on the other hand, they are not taken seriously enough by them. Modern

AI algorithms are even more invisible than the technologies they are embedded in. This allows them to constantly obtain user data, find connections invisible to humans, create user profiles, and influence their beliefs and consciousness. This results in bias in decision making, and therefore direct manipulation of human behavior [5], [6].

The paper [7] found that AI algorithms like ChatGPT do not have beliefs, but they reflect opinions learned through training, and these opinions can be tailored to the desired outcome. The best defense against this new form of AI influence on humans is to make it known to as many people as possible. Government regulation is expected to ensure transparency regarding the work of AI algorithms and their influence on human consciousness.

Microsoft is raising new societal issues such as the responsible design and use of AI, establishing ethical principles to protect people, and the impact of AI algorithms on employment and jobs. Principles of fairness, trustworthiness and security, privacy and security of personal data, inclusivity, transparency, and accountability are critical to addressing the social impacts of AI and building trust. This is especially important in today's environment, as AI algorithms become an increasingly important part of the products and services people use every day at work and at home [8].

Google's principles for using AI algorithms are identical to those of Microsoft. However, Google also highlights limiting principles, such as refusing to participate in the development of AI algorithms that could cause irreparable harm to humanity [9].

In 2021, UNESCO linked manipulation to the abuse of cognitive biases in its Recommendations on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence [10].

Based on surveys of representative groups (1506 and 500 people), it was found that large language AI algorithms such as GPT-3 form a certain point of view and can influence the consciousness of individuals [11]. This is carried out in three directions: norms of behavior; legal norms; information. Such influence is difficult to determine, since only choice architectures are visible, but the preferences of opinions built into the language AI algorithms are hidden from users.

AI language algorithms have an accidental influence on individuals' beliefs. The opinions they form may then vary depending on the user, product, and context. Therefore, interactions with AI language algorithms influence users' opinions, even if this happens unintentionally. Clearly, more care should be taken in choosing the opinions that developers build into AI language algorithms such as GPT-3.

Communication mediated by AI algorithms (AI-MC) influences the basic aspects of individuals' communication, such as interpersonal perception, performance of managerial tasks, etc. [12]. At the same time, the active and dynamic nature of AI algorithms can change the norms and dynamics of individuals' communication. These findings suggest that AI language algorithms are capable of undermining such aspects of interpersonal perception as social attraction.

An empirical test of the possibility of AI algorithms influencing people's preferences through explicit or implicit persuasion in various contexts was conducted in [13]. It was found that the speed and volume of research into the specifics of AI influence on the behavior of large groups of people conducted

by academic scientists are several times less than similar indicators of AI companies. The latter work with samples that are inaccessible to scientists due to their scale. Therefore, the most common AI algorithms are formed not as a result of scientific research, but in order to achieve specific private interests of these companies. Therefore, the ability of companies developing AI algorithms to influence the decisions of large groups of people and/or manipulate their behavior both explicitly and implicitly is certainly much higher.

Summarizing the results of the research in the first direction, we can conclude that the problem of AI manipulability exists and that new large-scale research is needed to solve it. At the same time, manipulability itself can be different - both intentional and accidental. Existing studies do not yet provide a clear understanding of the volume and degree of information manipulation that modern AI systems and algorithms have. To obtain specific assessments of this process, it is advisable to interpret the results in the language of mathematics. In this case, the problem is easily reduced to a shift in assessments and actions, narrowing their variability and identifying intentional and/or accidental AI manipulability.

2. The study of the influence of AI algorithms on the random and/or targeted change of the basic values of the Russian civilizational model and attempts to shift it to the Western liberal-fundamentalist model are covered in many works from a purely theoretical side [14], [15], [16]. At the same time, a fairly wide range of differences is used. Obviously, effective testing is impossible under such conditions. A basic set of fundamentally significant differences must be selected.

In general, it is enshrined in the Decree of the President of Russia No. 809 of November 9, 2022, which approved the "Fundamentals of State Policy for the Preservation and Strengthening of Traditional

Russian Spiritual and Moral Values." However, this document presents a descriptive justification for the values of Russian civilization.

We are interested in formalized assessments of the most significant civilizational values. They are available in the work [17]. A quantitative analysis of the values of Russia and Western countries was carried out based on G. Hofstede's methodology. The comparison was carried out on 5 main factors: individuality, distance from power, long-term orientation, certainty of the future, masculinity. As a result of the comparison with Western countries (USA, Great Britain, France, Germany) and Eastern countries (China, India, Japan, Pakistan), a fundamentally different axiological type of Russia was revealed. Its main value contradiction lies in the contradiction between individualism and collectivism.

Quantitative assessments of the value orientation of countries of the world are presented in the World Values Survey project, which has been implemented since 1981 and covers almost 100 countries. It is based on the results of surveys, which are assessed according to the system developed by the American political scientist and sociologist Ronald Inglehart (1934-2021). Two value dichotomies were used: tradition-secularity and collectivism-individualism. The correctness of the methodology used is confirmed by the clear distribution of different civilizational areas of countries into clusters. Russia and the entire "Orthodox" cluster of countries (marked in red) (see Fig. 1 [18]) are the most distant in terms of values from the clusters of the "Protestant" (marked in yellow) and "Anglo-Saxon" (marked in dark green) areas. The obtained quantitative results allow us to speak about the global alternative Russia – the West, since the areas of clusters of these countries have the highest indicator of value remoteness among all civilizations.

The Inglehart-Welzel World Cultural Map 2023

Fig. 1. Inglehart-Welzel's cultural map of the world.

The value orientations of the population of any country may change over time. Therefore, in addition to assessing the axiological differences of civilizations, it is necessary to identify the direction of value variability. In the long term, this will allow us to talk about the convergence or divergence of the values of different civilizations. The long-term implementation of the World Values Survey project allows us to identify the corresponding value trends, which will shape the value profile of countries and civilizations in the future (see Fig. 2[18]).

We have not found any other quantitatively systematized studies in this area. Therefore, the use of the "individualism-collectivism" factor fully reflects the chaos-order in public consciousness and is one

of the basic differences between the Russian civilizational model and the Western liberal-fundamentalist one.

Main part

The problem of the impact of AI on the consciousness of individuals, their groups and more broadly - on public consciousness can be reduced in the first approximation to the displacement of assessments and actions, their variability. Of particular interest is the random or systemic manipulation of AI. The significance for progress of the actually observed compression of the diversity of AI assessments and actions of agents for symmetrical relations is shown in the work [2].

Fig. 2. Dynamics of development of value systems in countries of the world (since 1981).

The significance of the problem under study is well illustrated by the results shown in Fig. 3 [1]. Fig. 4 from [2] presents typical results of the possible influence of AI algorithms on factors that are obviously

asymmetric to estimation errors and individual actions.

Fig. 3. Effect of variability (compiled by the authors).

Figures 3 and 4 illustrate the need for a differentiated approach to studying the influence of AI algorithms on public consciousness based on various factors. Given the impossibility of effectively assessing the manipulative influence of AI algorithms across the countless factors that determine the characteristics of the Russian civilizational model, we will justify the choice of basic factors. As is known, the

main measure of living systems is the ratio of "chaos and order". According to the authors, the "individualism-collectivism" factor fully reflects this ratio in public consciousness. In addition, this factor is one of the basic differences between the Russian civilizational model and the liberal-fundamentalist Western one [17].

Fig. 4. Evolution of the variable system (compiled by the authors).

Of greatest interest to our research is the assessment of the manipulability of specific AI. Since the set of basic factors and specific testing methods for the AI-People algorithms system have not yet been developed, then initially, for the assessment of the factors "individualism-collectivism" and "Machiavellianism", methods well-tested on people can be used. In this case, the "pseudo-personalities" generated by the AI algorithms will be considered as a group of "test personalities". During the experiment, we will compare them with a control group of real individuals. This approach allows us to use well-tested methods of social psychology.

Materials and methods

To conduct the study, two methods were selected:

- 1) a method for diagnosing a tendency to manipulation ("Machiavellism" – (hereinafter – M) - the Russian-language version of the Mach-4 scale;
- 2) a method for assessing the perceived culture of a community based on the cultural orientation "horizontal/vertical individualism – collectivism" (hereinafter – I-C).

They have satisfactory reliability and validity indicators. The methodology [19] allows diagnosing people's tendency to choose the basic cultural values of individualism and/or collectivism. The questionnaire "Horizontal/vertical individualism - collectivism" is used to obtain the results. Additional characteristics horizontal-vertical [20] are intended to specify the basic concepts in terms of the value of equality, on the one hand (horizontal axis), and hierarchy, on the other (vertical axis). The methodology consists of 16 statements / items (4 items for each axis (horizontal

individualism, vertical individualism, horizontal collectivism, vertical collectivism).

The method of assessing the tendency to manipulation [21] diagnoses people's tendency to manipulation (another term is Machiavellism) in behavior and communication. In this case, Machiavellianism is understood as a psychological syndrome based on the relationship between the cognitive, motivational and behavioral characteristics of an individual. The essential psychological components of Machiavellism are:

1) the individual's belief that when communicating with other people, they can and even should be manipulated;

2) skills, specific manipulation abilities as the ability to convince others, to understand their intentions and reasons for their actions [22].

The questionnaire includes 20 statements. The subject must express the extent of his agreement or disagreement with each of the 20 statements on a seven-point scale - from "Completely agree" (7 points) to "Completely disagree" (1 point).

The survey was conducted through the Anketolog service <https://anketolog.ru/>. Link to the questionnaire: <https://anketolog.ru/s/849940/LQ7fRY4K>.

The survey of the AI "pseudo-personalities" was conducted by the authors in writing, both questionnaires were presented sequentially to two AI: GPT-4 and IISbera (Giga-chat).

The results of AI and people were first processed in a standard way using keys for each of the methods. Then statistical processing methods were used: the Mann-Whitney criterion and the Mann-Whitney U-criterion were used. The choice of these criteria was due to the possibility of using them to identify differences in the value of a parameter between small samples. The obtained results of comparing the values of the selected parameters between AI and people are presented in Figures 5-10.

Results and discussion

There are significant differences (Fig. 5-6) between GPT-4 and humans, as well as between IISbera and humans for the M factor.

For the I-K factor values, the asymptotic significance was greater than 0.05. This means that no significant differences were found for these variables between the AI and Human groups (Fig. 5-10).

For illustration purposes, Figures 7 and 8 show the results of comparing the responses of GPT-4 and Sber's AI, on the one hand, and People, on the other, on the individualism variable. They show that the obtained values ($U_{emp} = 100$ and $U_{emp} = 80$, respectively) lie in the insignificance range.

Fig. 5. Comparison of GPT-4 and Human responses by Machiavellism.

Fig. 6. Comparison of responses of Sber AI (Giga-chat) and People according to Machiavellism.

A similar comparison of the results of GPT-4 and Sber AI, on the one hand, and People, on the other, for the collectivism variable (see Fig. 9 and 10)

showed that the obtained values ($U_{\text{emp.}} = 88$ and $U_{\text{emp.}} = 92$, respectively) lie in the range of insignificance.

Fig. 7. Comparison of GPT-4 and Human responses on Individualism.

The significance of the apparent Machiavellianism of AI, regardless of whether it is random or systemic, certainly seems dangerous. Unfortunately, the insignificance of the deviation of the averages on the

I-K factor does not yet allow for an unambiguous interpretation, since the “human” methodology of working on this scale involves data centering procedures. Perhaps we should think about adapting the methodology for AI.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the responses of AI Sber and People on Individualism.

Fig. 9. Comparison of GPT-4 AI and Human responses on Collectivism.

Fig. 10. Comparison of the responses of AI Sber and People on Collectivism.

The significance of the apparent Machiavellianism of AI, regardless of whether it is random or systemic, certainly seems dangerous. Unfortunately, the insignificance of the deviation of the averages for the I-K factor does not yet allow for an unambiguous interpretation, since the "human" methodology of working on this scale involves data centering procedures.

Perhaps, it is worth considering adapting the methodology for AI. Given the rather limited sample sizes for AI pseudo-personalities, we used the standard Fisher criterion with a standard significance level of 0.05 to assess the compression of diversity. For these pairs of samples, it is approximately equal to 2.5. At the same time, for AI-1 for factor M, we will get the value $F1 = 2.7$ and for AI-2, $F2 = 1.5$, which means the absence of significant compression of diversity for factor M.

According to the I-K factor, the assessments are quite definite: $F1=5$, $F2= 25$, that is, we have a clear significant narrowing of the diversity of assessments and actions. Considering the need for constant optimization of the chaos-order ratio in rapidly changing external conditions (see Fig. 10), this narrowing seems dangerous.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained during the study, the following conclusions were formulated.

The risks of introducing AI algorithms into the daily activities of individuals are one of the main topics of debate for both practitioners and theorists. The negative impact of narrowing variability for situations of symmetrical "bad" and "good" deviations has already been considered by the authors earlier. The obtained results predetermine the need to use a differentiated approach to assess the impact of AI algorithms on the consciousness of individuals and society as a whole according to various factors.

A systemic approach to the selection of management decisions that allow minimizing the risks of negative impact of AI algorithms on the civilizational features of Russia is substantiated. For its implementation, an experimental study of the impact of existing AI algorithms on collective consciousness was carried out according to two factors: individualism-collectivism and manipulateness (Machiavellism).

The choice of tests that have been well-developed on individuals is methodologically justified. Control groups of individuals were compared with groups of "personalities" generated by AI. The results were obtained on the basis of small samples, typical for the initial stage of experiments. According to the I-K factor, there is no bias in the estimates inherited by the AI algorithms, with an indisputable compression of variability for any accepted levels of significance. On the contrary, when assessing AI by the M

factor (as a measure of manipulability), the AI algorithms differ significantly from individuals in bias. Therefore, further research is necessary to obtain estimates of variability by the M factor.

Bibliography:

1. Grachev I.D., Noak N.V., Kostina T.A. Ambivalence of social ideas about AI: Psychology, statistics, forecasts // *Digital Economy*, No. 1 (27), 2024a. Pp. 54-61.

2. Grachev I.D., Noak N.V. Optimization of agent diversity: reflections, hypotheses, forecasts // *Digital Economy*, No. 2 (28), 2024v. June. Pp. 57-60.

3. Is Xi Jinping an AI doomer? China's elite is split over artificial intelligence // *The Economist* 25.08. 2024. <https://www.economist.com/china/2024/08/25/is-xi-jinping-an-ai-doomer>.

4. Volkova A.D., Kostina T.A., Noak N.V. Social representations of artificial intelligence: methodological aspects (Part 2) // *Digital economy*, 2023, No. 26(5). P. 18-28.

5. Klenk, M. (2022). (Online) manipulation: sometimes hidden, always careless. *Rev. Soc. Economy*. 80. P. 85-105. doi: 10.1080/00346764.2021.1894350.

6. Faraoni S. (2023) Persuasive technology and computational manipulation: excessive disregard for mental self-determination. // *Front. Artificial. Intelligence*. 6:1216340. doi: 10.3389/frai.2023.1216340.

7. Xu, J., Ju, D., Li, M., Boureau, Y., Weston, J., and Dinan, E. Bot-adversarial dialogue for safe conversational agents. In *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, 2021.

8. Smith B., Shum H. *The Future Computed: Artificial Intelligence and Its Role in Society*. Washington, Microsoft Corporation, 2018. 143 p.

9. Why Google thinks we need to regulate AI // *Financial Times*. URL: <https://www.ft.com/content/3467659a-386d-11ea-ac3c-f68c10993b04>.

10. UNESCO. (2021). «UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence» (23 November 2021). SHS/BIO/PI/2021/1. Paris: UNESCO.

11. Jakesch M., Bhat A., Buschek D., Zalmanson L., and Naaman M., 2023. Co-Writing with Opinionated Language Models Affects Users' Views. In *Proceedings of the 2023 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '23)*, April 23-28, 2023, Hamburg, Germany. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 15 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3544548.3581196>.

12. Jahanbakhsh F., Zhang A.X., Berinsky A. J., Pennycook G., Rand D.G. and David R. Karger. 2021. Exploring Lightweight Interventions at Posting Time to Reduce the Sharing of Misinformation on Social Media. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.* 5, CSCW1, Article 18 (April 2021), 42 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3449092>.

13. Agudo U, Matute H (2021) The influence of algorithms on political and dating decisions. *PLoS ONE* 16(4): e0249454. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0249454>.

14. Pantin V.I. Civilizational Features of Russia's Development in the Context of Modern Social Transformations // *Bulletin of the Institute of Sociology*. 2021. Vol. 12. No. 4. P. 108-124. DOI: 10.19181/vis.2021.12.4.754.

15. Savin S.D., Kasabutskaya M.S. National Russian values in the context of the formation of collective identity // *Bulletin of St. Petersburg University. Sociology*. 2019. Vol. 12. Issue. 1. Pp. 82-97. <https://doi.org/10.21638/spbu12.2019.106>.

16. Semenova D.M., Afonin M.V., Kudryavtsev S.A. Values in the structure of civic identity: concept and tools // *Political consultant*, 2023. Vol. 3. No. 1. URL: <https://politicaljournal.ru/PDF/04PK123.pdf>.

17. Values of Russian civilization: a methodological manual for universities. / V.E. Baghdasaryan, Yu.Yu. Ierusalimsky. Yaroslavl: IPK "Indigo", 2023. - 80 p.

18. World Values Survey Association (WVSA). Materials of the official website. [Electronic resource]. URL - <https://www.worldvaluessurvey.org/WVSNewsShowMore.jsp?evYEAR=2023&evMONTH=-1>.

19. Galliamova A.A., Grigoriev D.S. Development of a methodology for assessing the perceived culture of a community based on the cultural orientation "horizontal / vertical individualism - collectivism" of G. Triandis // *Bulletin of RUDN. Series: Psychology and Pedagogy*. 2022. No. 3. P. 429-447.

20. Singelis, T. M., Triandis, H. C., Bhawuk, D. P. S., & Gelfand, M. J. (1995). Horizontal and vertical dimensions of individualism and collectivism: A theoretical and measurement refinement. *Cross-Cultural Research*, No. 29 (3). Pp. 240-275. <https://doi.org/10.1177/106939719502900302>.

21. Znakov, V. V. *Psychology of Understanding: Problems and Prospects*. Moscow: Institute of Psychology of the Russian Academy of Sciences, 2005. - 448 p.

22. *Studies in Machiavellianism* / Ed. by Christie R., Geis F. L. New York: Academic Press, 1970.